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TA'LIMDA TILLARNI O'QITISHNING MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI

**ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЯЗЫКОВОГО
ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ПУТИ ИХ РЕШЕНИЯ**

**PROBLEMS OF LANGUAGE
LEARNING AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM**

MAVZUSIDAGI XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA

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INTEGRATING SOFT SKILLS INTO LANGUAGE ASSESSMENT: A PRAGMATIC APPROACH FOR 21ST CENTURY LEARNERS

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Annotation: The era of technological advancements requires 21st-century learners and educators to keep up with emerging trends for both professional and personal growth. Today, many language learners can easily obtain linguistic knowledge across various fields. In the global labor market, however, there is a growing demand for individuals who is able not only apply acquired linguistic knowledge, but also cooperate effectively with others, solve complex problems, and show emotional and pragmatic awareness in real-life contexts. Even though communicative competence is emphasized, many language tests still give more weight to linguistic accuracy rather than practical communication abilities. In a globalized environment, this causes a disconnect between the goals of instruction and assessment the real needs of learners. These expectations highlight the need for language material development to move beyond a narrow focus on the cognitive domain and include social and communicative dimensions of language use. Therefore, in an attempt to align with global frameworks such as OECD's Education 2030 and the Partnership for 21st Century Learning (P21), this **thesis** explores methods of integrating soft skills into reading and listening tasks.

Key words: decision making, critical thinking, collaboration, soft skills, listening and reading skills.

Annotatsiya: Texnologik taraqqiyot davri 21-asr o'quvchilari va o'qituvchilaridan professional hamda shaxsiy rivojlanish uchun yangi tendensiyalarni kuzatib borishni talab qilmoqda. Bugungi kunda ko'plab til o'rganuvchilar turli sohalar bo'yicha lingvistik bilimlarni osongina egallash imkoniyatiga egadirlar. Biroq global mehnat bozorida faqat til bilimini qo'llay oladigan emas, balki samarali hamkorlik qila oladigan, murakkab muammolarni hal

eta oladigan va real hayotiy vaziyatlarda emotsional va pragmatik ongni namoyon eta oladigan mutaxassislarga talab ortib bormoqda. Garchi kommunikativ kompetensiyaga katta e'tibor qaratilsa-da, ko'plab til testlari hanuzgacha grammatik aniqlikka amaliy muloqot qobiliyatlariga nisbatan ko'proq ahamiyat berib kelmoqda. Bunday holat globallashtirilgan muhitda ta'lim maqsadlari bilan baholash mezonlari o'rtasida nomuvofiqlikka olib keladi. Shu bois, til materiallarini ishlab chiqishda faqat bilish (kognitiv) doirasigagina qaratilgan yondashuvdan voz kechib, tilning ijtimoiy va kommunikativ jihatlarini ham qamrab oluvchi uslublarni ishlab chiqish zarurati paydo bo'lmoqda. Mazkur dissertatsiyada ana shu ehtiyojni inobatga olgan holda, OECD'ning "Education 2030" tashabbusi va P21 (21-asr uchun ta'lim hamkorligi) kabi global tamoyillarga muvofiq holda, yumshoq ko'nikmalarni (soft skills) o'qish va tinglab tushunish topshiriqlariga integratsiya qilish usullari o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: qaror qabul qilish, tanqidiy fikrlash, hamkorlik, yumshoq ko'nikmalar, tinglab tushunish va o'qish ko'nikmalari.

Acquiring a foreign language requires individuals to possess both linguistic competence and social skills since language fundamentally develops through human interaction (Krashen, 1982, p. 31). This view is supported by the Affective Filter Hypothesis, which emphasizes that emotional factors- such as motivation, anxiety, and self-confidence - affect the success of language acquisition (Krashen, 1982, p. 31). Learners are more likely to communicate and retain new language material when they feel emotionally stable and confident. In this context, the skills are problem solving, decision making, critical thinking and most importantly effective communication. Similarly, there is a related approach called Social-Emotional Learning (SEL), which promotes the incorporation of five core interpersonal skills (CASEL, 2020) - social awareness, self-management, responsible decision-making, self-awareness, and relationship skills - to foster the learners to have meaningful interaction. The latter of these mentioned skills fully coincides with soft skill components: communication, active listening, cooperation, teamwork, and conflict

resolution. Pertaining to this matter, studies by Kalyana (2019, p. 89) suggest that soft skills are a prerequisite for language learners to excel in real-life applications of language in the workplace or in other social settings.

Modern language acquisition approaches increasingly emphasize a real-life social context over isolated vocabulary and grammar aspects of the language. Therein, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) method underscores to what extent the learner is able to use language meaningfully in specific situations, rather than demonstrating the learner's metalinguistic knowledge (Richards & Rodgers, 2014, p. 85). This theoretical shift also holds the ground for the implementation of soft skills such as critical thinking and collaboration.

A framework that prioritizes the inclusion of soft skills into language instruction and assessment is Partnership for 21st Century Learning (P21). The core outline of this framework underscores the integration of the "4Cs" that are creativity, communication, collaboration, and critical thinking into all subjects (Battelle for Kids, 2019). It has been recognized globally by organizations like OECD and UNESCO, underlining the point that not only academic knowledge should be prevalent but also students' ability to engage in teamwork and decision making skills in problematic situations. In this regard, the framework Education 2030 by OECD entails a special category named "transformative competencies" – reconciling dilemmas and tensions that mainly spotlights the learner empathy and respect towards different perceptions. (OECD, 2018, p. 4).

Since soft skills involve empathy, socio-pragmatic awareness, and evaluative thinking, assessment tasks designed to assess them will inexorably be connected with inferencing the meaning, evaluating communicative behavior and providing response accordingly. Therefore, these principles closely mirror the categories of higher order thinking skills. When designing reading and listening skills, test developers should aim to replicate real-life language use rather than isolate grammar and vocabulary items. For instance, test content should be enriched with dialogues, scenarios, narratives so as to engage the learner to interpret the speaker emotions, intentions, and implied meaning.

The comprehension questions categorized as higher order thinking stress the understanding that go beyond literal meaning. As identified by Days and Park [2005, p. 64] there is taxonomy of comprehension questions which include inference, evaluation and personal response. Thus, item writers should consider deliberate inclusion of questions focusing on empathy – inferring characters’ attitudes or emotions, critical thinking and ethics (evaluate the actions), and (personal reflection) ability to relate the task to personal experience.

Moreover, there are integrated and task based formats of questions which provide the best practice of soft skills. In this case the task will evolve around the certain problematic scenario presented in audio listening or reading format. For instance, listening item might feature a short dialogue between two individuals collaborating to reach a decision, allowing test taker to understand each person’s perspective and the decision reached. This assess not only collaborative process but also the ability to follow a collaborative process and identify effective contributions. Scenario-based assessments - where a series of items revolve around a common real world scenario - test takers must apply language skills and judgement. [Douglas, 2000, p. 47].

Designing the test items could focus on soft skills when “empathy and perspective-taking” approach is implemented. The test is generated by taking culturally diverse situations with empathy-related questions. The test taker is supposed to infer the character’s emotion from the context. Unlike traditional test items that evolve around recalling factual information, soft skill-informed tasks rely on test takers’ ability to pick up indirect cues and the subtext of communication, thus demonstrating socio-pragmatic competence [Fulcher & Davidson, 2007, p. 145].

In the context of language assessment, soft skill-oriented items should maintain the balance and validity. The aim of these tasks is to evaluate English proficiency by integrating soft skills. An important aspect of creating prompts for stems and answers is that they should be adequately language-focused so that when the wrong answer is provided, it should indicate the comprehension issue, not the difference of personal values. For the test developers, piloting is of paramount

importance as it gives clues whether the item differentiates the test takers on their language ability or other irrelevant factors. For instance, questions testing decision-making skills should be based solely on the information depicted in the text of the listening or reading task, not on the test takers own moral beliefs. In this perspective, choosing the best decision is the result of a good understanding of the task.

References:

1. Battelle for Kids. (2019). *Framework for 21st Century Learning*.
2. Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL). (2020). *Core SEL Competencies*.
3. Douglas, D. (2000). *Assessing Languages for Specific Purposes*. Cambridge University Press.
4. Fulcher, G., & Davidson, F. (2007). *Language Testing and Assessment: An Advanced Resource Book*.
5. Kalyana, M. (2019). *Soft Skills for Employability: Need for Greater Emphasis in Curriculum*. *International Journal of Applied Research*.
6. Krashen, S. D. (1982). *Principles and Practice in Second Language Acquisition*.
7. OECD. (2018). *The Future of Education and Skills: Education 2030*.
8. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2014). *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching*.